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Adaptive, Predictive 3-D Geologic Modeling in Hard Rock Tunneling Projects

Ashton Krajnovich¹, Wendy Zhou¹, Marte Gutierrez¹
¹ Colorado School of Mines

INTRODUCTION

The increased use and complexity of constructing and maintaining underground spaces call for more advanced techniques for better understanding the subsurface conditions. A 3-dimensional (3-D) geologic model can be an important tool for filling this gap, i.e. informing effective design of a tunneling project. Traditionally, only the geology along the tunnel transect is considered using cross-sections to establish baseline geologic conditions. However, the 3-D geologic model can be used to incorporate more realistic interpretations of the subsurface into the geologic baselines, and as a tool to intuitively communicate these results to designers. In recent years, novel modeling methods and the widespread availability of computer memory allows for faster, more efficient creation of 3-D geologic models.

The extreme depth and lateral extent of hard rock tunnels often results in highly uncertain geologic characterization. This issue is compounded by inflexible tunnel design and construction leading to a prevalent issue in tunneling projects: unexpected ground conditions leading to project stoppages. Any and all available subsurface information must be incorporated into the geologic model to improve predictions and reduce structural uncertainty in order to inform effective tunnel design and avoid encountering unexpected ground conditions.

As excavation progresses, new information on the encountered geologic units/structures can be acquired to validate and update the geologic model. Compared to traditional, explicit modeling techniques, implicit modeling allows for increased efficiency and autonomy in the geologic model creation process. This streamlined workflow opens new possibilities for utilizing the geologic model as a design tool, including the ability to incorporate new and varied data and perturb input parameters to test geologic predictions and characterize model uncertainty. Implicit modeling also bypasses the inflexible meshing requirements of explicit methods, resulting in a model which can be adapted to fit various numerical modeling schemes used to design tunnel support requirements.

Rockmass consists of intact rock and discontinuities (e.g. joints, faults, bedding planes, and foliations). Prior to tunneling in hard rock, the discontinuity condition of the rockmass must

be interpolated between and extrapolated from initial observations, i.e. borings and outcrops. A more robust approach than interpolating numerical values of rockmass quality (e.g. Rock Mass Rating, Q-system) involves the interpolation of the discontinuity surfaces themselves.

Here we utilize implicit geologic modeling using the potential-field method to use data collected during excavation to characterize the extent of encountered discontinuities in order to better inform the extrapolation of these surfaces beyond the tunnel face. Various extrapolation approaches can be used in modeling to create multiple realistic models from the same input data. Encountered geology (from excavation or additional investigations) will be used to validate these models and select the best-fit extrapolation method for the project setting. Realistic uncertainty quantification can be achieved using an ensemble of models which account for error propagation from uncertainty in the input data and the modeling process into the resultant model. Incorporating the improved understanding of geologic uncertainty into the baseline conditions will be a future application of this work.

RESEACRH OBJECTIVES

Using regional geologic knowledge, generate predictions to extrapolate structures from sparse observations, utilizing the autonomy of implicit geologic modeling to create multiple models respecting the hard data via different interpretations. Synthetic data will be used to enforce realistic geologic predictions during model creation. Predicted models will be validated against newly acquired data, from excavation mapping or additional investigations, to select the ‘best-fit’ prediction to update geologic interpretations. Statistical tools such as cross-validation and % misfit can be used in tandem with interpretive use of geologic knowledge to eliminate unrealistic models and provide a degree of validation for others. Incorporating the new data and updated geologic predictions, the 3-D geologic model can be iteratively updated until a full characterization of the geology encountered along the excavation is achieved. Uncertainty can be quantified at any stage of modeling using an ensemble of equiprobable models to communicate the degree of variability in the expected geology.

METHODOLOGY

- I. Preliminary site investigations (boreholes, surface observations, regional geology)
- II. Extrapolate structures between sparse observations using synthetic data
- III. Implicit modeling to create multiple models testing geologic predictions
- IV. Define current geologic baseline conditions and inform empirical design and numerical modeling
- V. Acquire new data through additional investigations or excavation mapping
- VI. Validate current model against encountered geology, select ‘best-fit’ interpretation
- VII. Update predictions, characterize model uncertainty
- VIII. Continue from step IV

End Result: Fully characterized 3-D geologic model for maintenance reliability and longevity

PRELIMINARY RESULTS – N/A

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